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Health Resources Utilization and poverty reduction: An example of innovative therapeutic strategy to reduce the burden on the health system in the developing countries contributing to poverty reduction

Al Mosawi AJ

The judicious utilization of the resources available to the health system in the developing world is an integral part of the healthy system reform and may represent a contributing factor to poverty reduction in these countries. The introduction of the modern technologic advances in the management of certain chronic disorders that require life long care (e.g. end-stage renal failure) may not be possible in many countries with fragile health care system. In some countries only adults can be provided to some extent these therapeutic technologies. Introducing a less expensive and easy available medical therapeutic advances can be both useful and rewarding.

Patients with end-stage renal failure (ESRF) and glomerular filtration rates less than 5% of the normal can't sustain life in the absence of renal replacement therapy (RRT), and either dialysis or transplantation is required. RRT is widely available in industrialized countries. In developing countries they are not uniformly available, so patient's management often relies on the conservative measures and intermittent peritoneal dialysis (IPD). ESRF patients treated in such way may die from uremia and complications of IPD.

Dialysis and transplantation (RRT) were originally developed to forestall death in patients with ESRF has become the standard management in the developed countries. However in many areas of the world RRT is considered extremely expensive in both manpower and money, with a maintenance cost far beyond costs contracted in other areas of the medical care. In developed countries RRT is considered the standard in the management of ESRF. RRT requires an expert team consisting of at least a nephrologist, cardiovascular surgeon, and urologist in addition to a skilled nursing staff. In areas where RRT introduced to some extent (e.g. hemodialysis and transplantation) despite the lack of effective and skilled teams, rehabilitation is commonly not satisfactory and the results are discouraging relative to costs in manpower and money. Patients undergoing RRT in such areas are commonly experiencing disproportionate amount of discomfort and suffering not balanced by the added length of life achieved. On the other hand many patients particularly children don't have any access to any form of RRT. These children will usually managed by intermittent acute peritoneal dialysis with death is the ultimate outcome. In the last few years confronted with unpalatable spectacular of the suffering of children with ESRD, a novel therapeutic strategy to provide these children with dialysis freedom and improved wellbeing has been investigated.

Correspondent author:

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi MD, Ph.D.
Director Postspecialty CME center
Al- Kadhimiyia University Hospital.
Baghdad, Iraq

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